

PRIME, SEMIPRIME AND K-IDEALS IN B-SEMIRINGS

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Abstract—

In this paper, we introduce some basic concept of prime, semi-prime, k-ideals and minimal prime divisor of ideals in b-semirings. We have analyzed some results on prime, semi-prime, k-ideals, radicals of ideals in b-semirings.

Keywords— b-semiring, Ideals, Prime Ideals, k-ideals, Radicals, Semi-Prime Ideals,.

1 Introduction

The concept of b-semirings was introduced by Chinram [1] in 2008. As semirings have broad Applications in the mathematical foundations of computer science [4] and b-semirings constitute Natural generalization of semirings, hence b-semirings also have the broad applications in Computer Sciences. In this paper we have proved theorems based on semi-prime ideals, prime ideals, k-ideals, radicals of ideals in b-semiring. For the sake of convenience we use the term ideal only in place of b-semiring ideal.

A. b-Semiring

Definition [1]: A set S with two binary compositions $\circ_1$ and $\circ_2$ is said to be a b-semiring if for all $a, b, c \in S$ it must satisfy

$$(i) a \circ_1 (b \circ_2 c) = (a \circ_1 b) \circ_2 (a \circ_1 c) \text{ and } (b \circ_2 c) \circ_1 a = (b \circ_1 a) \circ_2 (c \circ_1 a)$$

$$(ii) a \circ_2 (b \circ_1 c) = (a \circ_2 b) \circ_1 (a \circ_2 c) \text{ and } (b \circ_1 c) \circ_2 a = (b \circ_2 a) \circ_1 (c \circ_2 a).$$

Further $(S, \circ_1, \circ_2)$ is called a Commutative b-semiring if

$$a \circ_1 b = b \circ_1 a \quad \text{And}$$

$$a \circ_2 b = b \circ_2 a \quad \forall a, b \in S.$$

B. Ideal In b-Semiring

Definition [1]: Let $(S, \circ_1, \circ_2)$ be a b-semiring. A nonempty subset L of S is called a left ideal of S if $s \circ_1 a \in L$ and $s \circ_2 a \in L$ for all $a \in L$ and $s \in L$.

Let $(S, \circ_1, \circ_2)$ be a b-semiring. A nonempty subset R of S is called a right ideal of S if $a \circ_1 s \in L$ and $a \circ_2 s \in L$ for all $a \in L$ and $s \in R$.

1. Right and Left Ideals

Definition 1.1 [1]: Let (S, σ_1, σ_2) be a b-semiring. A subset I of S is called an ideal if both I is Left as well as right ideal of S . i.e

- (i) $s\sigma_1 a \in I$ and $s\sigma_2 a \in I$ for all $a \in I$ and $s \in I$.
- (ii) $a\sigma_1 s \in I$ and $a\sigma_2 s \in I$ for all $a \in I$ and $s \in I$.

2. Proper Ideal

Definition 2.1 [1]: Suppose (S, σ_1, σ_2) be a b-semiring and I is an ideal of S , We Say that I is a proper ideal if I is not equal to S .

3. Prime Ideals In b-Semirings

We define prime ideals in b-semirings as follows:

Definition 3.1: An Ideal I of a b-semiring S is called prime if whenever $a\sigma_1 S\sigma_1 b \subseteq I$ And $a\sigma_2 S\sigma_2 b \subseteq I$,

- (i) $a\sigma_1 b \in I$
- (ii) $a\sigma_2 b \in I$ Implies that $a \in I$ or $b \in I$.

Example 3.2: Let A be a b-semiring. $A = \{\emptyset, \{1\}, \{2\}, \{1,2\}\}$ is a discrete topological space of N Under the operations $\cup$ and $\cap$. Then A is prime ideal of S .

Theorem 3.3: An deal I of a b-semiring (S, σ_1, σ_2) is prime if $R\sigma_1 L \subseteq I, R\sigma_2 L \subseteq I$ With R a right ideal and L a left ideal of (S, σ_1, σ_2) implies $R \subseteq I$ or $L \subseteq I$.

Proof: Let (S, σ_1, σ_2) is a b-semiring and I be a prime ideal of (S, σ_1, σ_2) with $R\sigma_1 L \subseteq I$ and $R\sigma_2 L \subseteq I$.

Further suppose that $R \subseteq S$ for all $x \in S$ and $r \in R/S$,

Then we have $r\sigma_1 I\sigma_1 x \subseteq R\sigma_1 L \subseteq S$ and $r\sigma_2 I\sigma_2 x \subseteq R\sigma_2 L \subseteq S$.

Since I is prime and $r \in B$, we have $x \in S \forall x \in L$. So $L \subseteq I$. Similarly, we can show that $R \subseteq I$. Conversely,

Suppose $R\sigma_1 L \subseteq I$ and $R\sigma_2 L \subseteq I \Rightarrow R \subseteq I$ Or $L \subseteq I$ for any R as a right ideal and L as a left ideal of (S, σ_1, σ_2) . Let $x, y \in S$ such that $x\sigma_1 S \subseteq I, x\sigma_2 S \subseteq I$, and $\sigma_1 y \in I, S\sigma_2 y \in I$,

$$(x\sigma_1 S)\sigma_1 (S\sigma_1 y) \subseteq I, (x\sigma_2 S)\sigma_2 (S\sigma_2 y) \subseteq I.$$

Here $x\sigma_1 x \in I$ and $x\sigma_2 x \in I$ and $y\sigma_1 y \in I$ and $y\sigma_2 y \in I$

Again consider $(x)_r$ and $(x)_l$ be the right as well as left ideal of (S, σ_1, σ_2) generated by x in S .

Let z be any element of the product $(x)_r (x)_l$,

$$z = \sum_{i=1}^n (n_i x + x a_i) [p_i x + b_i x] \quad n_i, p_i \in Z \text{ and } a_i, b_i \in S.$$

$$z = \sum_{i=1}^n n_i k_i x^2 + n_i x b_i x + p_i x a_i x + x a_i b_i x + \dots \dots \dots$$

Since $x\sigma_1 x \in I$ and $x\sigma_2 x \in I$ and $b_i x, a_i x, a_i b_i x$ are all of S and $\sigma_1 S \subseteq I, \sigma_2 S \subseteq I$,

We have $z \in I$, Hence $(x)_r (x)_l \subseteq I$,

For our assumption $(x)_r \subseteq I$ and $(x)_l \subseteq I$,

Therefore $x \in I$, similarly $S\sigma_1 y \subseteq I, S\sigma_2 y \subseteq I$, therefore $y \in I$

And therefore I is a prime ideal of S . Hence Proved.

Proposition 3.4: A prime ideal I of a b-semiring (S, σ_1, σ_2) , is a prime one sided ideal of (S, σ_1, σ_2) .

Proof: Let I be a prime ideal of a b-semiring (S, σ_1, σ_2) ,

Then we have to show that I is one sided ideal of (S, σ_1, σ_2) .

By Definition
 $\implies (I\sigma_1 S)\sigma_1(S\sigma_1 I) \subseteq I \subseteq S$ and $(I\sigma_2 S)\sigma_2(S\sigma_2 I) \subseteq I \subseteq S$.

$I\sigma_1 S$ and $I\sigma_2 S$ are right ideals and $S\sigma_1 I$ and $S\sigma_2 I$ are left ideals of I .

$I\sigma_1 S \subseteq I$, $I\sigma_2 S \subseteq I$ And $(S\sigma_1 I) \subseteq I$, $(S\sigma_2 I) \subseteq I$.

Therefore I is one sided ideal of (S, σ_1, σ_2) .

I is any ideal of (S, σ_1, σ_2) , $L(I) = \{x \in I / S\sigma_1 x \subseteq I, S\sigma_2 x \subseteq I\}$ And

$H(I) = \{y \in L(I) / y\sigma_1 S \subseteq L(I), y\sigma_2 S \subseteq L(I)\}$

If $x \in L(I)$ and $z \in S$. then $z\sigma_1 x \in S\sigma_1 x \subseteq I$ and $z\sigma_2 x \in S\sigma_2 x \subseteq I$ and $S\sigma_1(z\sigma_1 x) \in S\sigma_1 x \subseteq I$,

$S\sigma_2(z\sigma_2 x) \in S\sigma_2 x \subseteq I$ $L(I)$ is a left ideal of S and $L(I) \subseteq I$.

Proposition 3.5: If I is any ideal of a b-semiring (S, σ_1, σ_2) , then $H(I)$ is the unique largest two sided ideal of (S, σ_1, σ_2) contained in I .

Proof: Let I be any ideal of S , we have $L(I) \subseteq I$ and $H(I) \subseteq L(I)$,

We have that $H(I) \subseteq I$, we now show that $H(I)$ is a two-sided ideal of S .

Let $x \in H(I)$ and $y \in S$, Then $x \in I$ and since x is also an element of $L(I)$,

We have that $S\sigma_1 x \subseteq I$, $S\sigma_2 x \subseteq I$ And $x\sigma_1 S \subseteq L(I)$, $x\sigma_2 S \subseteq L(I)$.

Then $y\sigma_1 x \in S\sigma_1 x \subseteq I$, $y\sigma_2 x \in S\sigma_2 x \subseteq I$, So $y\sigma_1 x \in I$, $y\sigma_2 x \in I$.

Further more $\sigma_1(y\sigma_1 x) \subseteq S\sigma_1 x \subseteq I$, $\sigma_2(y\sigma_2 x) \subseteq S\sigma_2 x \subseteq I$.

So $y\sigma_1 x \in L(I)$, $y\sigma_2 x \in L(I)$.

Also $x\sigma_1 y \in x\sigma_1 S \subseteq L(I)$, $x\sigma_2 y \in x\sigma_2 S \subseteq L(I)$.

Hence $(x\sigma_1 y) \in L(I)$ and $(x\sigma_2 y) \in L(I)$.

We must now show that $y\sigma_1 x \in H(I)$, $y\sigma_2 x \in H(I)$ and $x\sigma_1 y \in H(I)$, $x\sigma_2 y \in H(I)$.

$(x\sigma_1 y)\sigma_1 S \subseteq x\sigma_1 S \subseteq L(I)$,

$(x\sigma_2 y)\sigma_2 S \subseteq x\sigma_2 S \subseteq L(I)$. Hence $x\sigma_1 y \in H(I)$ and $x\sigma_2 y \in H(I)$.

Now $(y\sigma_1 x)\sigma_1 S \subseteq (S\sigma_1 x)\sigma_1 S \subseteq L(I)$, And $(y\sigma_2 x)\sigma_2 S \subseteq (S\sigma_2 x)\sigma_2 S \subseteq L(I)$.

Since $L(I)$ is a left ideal of S , Hence $y\sigma_1 x \in H(I)$ and $y\sigma_2 x \in H(I)$.

Let I_1 be another ideal of S be such that $I_1 \subseteq L(I)$ and let c be any arbitrary element of I_1 ,

Then $c \in I$ and $S\sigma_1 c \subseteq I_1 \subseteq I$, $S\sigma_2 c \subseteq I_1 \subseteq I$ Hence $I_1 \subseteq L(I)$.

Again if $c \in L(I)$ and $c\sigma_1 S \subseteq I_1 \subseteq L(I)$, $c\sigma_2 S \subseteq I_1 \subseteq L(I)$. this implies $c \in H(I)$ and hence $I_1 \subseteq H(I)$.

Theorem 3.6: If I be a prime ideal of a b-semiring (S, σ_1, σ_2) then $H(I)$ is a prime ideal in (S, σ_1, σ_2) .

Proof: Let I be any prime ideal in (S, σ_1, σ_2) , then for any two ideals X and Y in S ,

$X\sigma_1 Y \subseteq I$, $X\sigma_2 Y \subseteq I \implies X \subseteq I$ or $Y \subseteq I$.

And we have $H(I)$ as the largest ideal in (S, σ_1, σ_2) , Therefore $X \subseteq H(I)$ or $Y \subseteq H(I)$,

So, $X\sigma_1 Y \subseteq I \subseteq H(I)$ and $X\sigma_2 Y \subseteq I \subseteq H(I)$, hence $X\sigma_1 Y \subseteq H(I)$ and $X\sigma_2 Y \subseteq H(I)$,

Thus $H(I)$ is a prime ideal of (S, σ_1, σ_2) .

Corollary 3.7: A prime ideal of a commutative b-semiring is also commutative.

$(N, \min, \max)$ is a b-semiring,

We can define a prime ideal from N with $\min$ and $\max$ as two binary operations and for that $a \min b = \min(a, b)$ and $b \min a = \min(b, a)$.

Similarly, $a \max b = \max(a, b)$ and $b \max a = \max(b, a)$.

4. Semiprime Ideal in a b-Semiring.

Definition 4.1: An ideal A of a commutative b-semiring (S, σ_1, σ_2) is called a semi-prime ideal of a b-semiring (S, σ_1, σ_2) if for each $a \in A$,

$$a \sigma_1 a = a \text{ for } a \in A$$

$$a \sigma_2 a = a \text{ for } a \in A.$$

Example 4.2: Let A be a subset of $(P(X) \cup, \cup)$ with the operation $\cup$ as a binary operation

And A is a b-semiring, then A is a semiprime ideal of b-semiring $(P(X), \cup, \cup)$.

As $a \cup a = a$ for each $a \in A$.

Proposition 4.3: Let I be a semiprime ideal of a b-semiring (S, σ_1, σ_2) , then

$L\sigma_1 L \subseteq I, L\sigma_2 L \subseteq I$ Or $R\sigma_1 R \subseteq I, R\sigma_2 R \subseteq I$ implies that $L \subseteq I$ or $R \subseteq I$ for any L as a left ideal of S and R as a right ideal of S .

Proof: Given (S, σ_1, σ_2) as a b-semiring and I as an Ideal of (S, σ_1, σ_2) . Let L be a left ideal of I , be such that $L\sigma_1 L \subseteq I, L\sigma_2 L \subseteq I$.

Suppose L is not a subset of I then there exist an $x \in L, x \notin I$. Furthermore,

$$x\sigma_1(S\sigma_1 x) \subseteq L\sigma_1(S\sigma_1 x) \subseteq L\sigma_1 L \subseteq I \text{ and}$$

$$x\sigma_2(S\sigma_2 x) \subseteq L\sigma_2(S\sigma_2 x) \subseteq L\sigma_2 L \subseteq I.$$

Since I is semiprime, we have that $x \in I$, a contradiction. Hence $L \subseteq I$.

Similarly, we can prove that $R\sigma_1 R \subseteq I, R\sigma_2 R \subseteq I$.

Let (S, σ_1, σ_2) be a b-semiring, if I be any ideal of S . Further let

$$L(I) = (x \in I/x\sigma_1 S \subseteq I, x\sigma_2 S \subseteq I), H(I) = (y \in I/S\sigma_1 y \subseteq I, S\sigma_2 y \subseteq I).$$

Then $L(I)$ is a left ideal of S . Hence $L(I) \subseteq I$.

Proposition 4.4: Let I be a semiprime Ideal of a b-semiring S , then $H(I)$ is a semiprime Ideal of S .

Proof: Let I be a semiprime ideal of a b-semiring (S, σ_1, σ_2) and suppose $X\sigma_1 X \subseteq H(I), X\sigma_2 X \subseteq H(I)$

For any two sided ideal X of S . we have that

$X \subseteq I$ And thus from above, we have $X \subseteq H(I)$. Therefore $H(I)$ is a semi prime ideal.

5. k-Ideals In b-Semiring

Definition 5.1: Let A and B are two b-semirings ideals of a b-semiring (S, σ_1, σ_2) .

Then $\bar{A} = \{\bar{a} \in S | \text{there is some } a \in A \text{ such that } a\sigma_1 \bar{a} \in A \text{ and } a\sigma_2 \bar{a} \in A\}$. defines a b-semiring ideal $\bar{A}$ of (S, σ_1, σ_2) .

Definition 5.2: Let (S, σ_1, σ_2) be a b-semiring and A be a b-semiring ideal, suppose b-semiring $\bar{A}$

Ideal obtained from A by above definition, is called the closure of A . When $A = \bar{A}$. (A is called k-closed).

Example 5.3: We have that $(N, \min, \max)$ is a b-semiring. Further define

$$A_{a o_1 c} = \{a/ \text{ such that } a \leq c \text{ for all } c \in N\} \text{ and}$$

$$A_{a o_2 c} = \{a/ \text{ such that } a \leq c \text{ for all } c \in N\}.$$

Then $A_{a o_1 c}$ and $A_{a o_2 c}$ are ideals of $(N, \min, \max)$. Now consider another sets,

$$\bar{A}_{a o_1 c} = (\bar{a}/ \text{ such that } \bar{a} o_1 a \in A_{a o_1 c}) \text{ and.}$$

$$\bar{A}_{a o_2 c} = (\bar{b}/ \text{ such that } \bar{b} o_2 a \in A_{a o_1 c}).$$

Then we observe that $\bar{A}_{a o_1 c}$ and $\bar{A}_{a o_2 c}$ are also an ideal, these are called k -ideals. Further if

$A_{a o_1 c} = \bar{A}_{a o_1 c}$ and $A_{a o_2 c} = \bar{A}_{a o_2 c}$ then $A_{a o_1 c}$ and $A_{a o_2 c}$ is called k -closed ideal.

Lemma 5.4: Let A be an ideal of (S, o_1, o_2) then

$$\bar{A} = \{a \in S: a o_1 x \in A, a o_2 x \in A \text{ for some } x \in A\} \text{ is an ideal of } S.$$

Proof: Let $a, b \in \bar{A}$, then $a o_1 x, b o_1 y \in A$, for some $x, y \in A$.

Now $a o_1 x o_1 b o_1 y = (a o_1 b) o_1 (x o_1 y) \in A$. As $x o_1 y \in A$ and $a o_1 b \in \bar{A}$.

Similarly $a o_2 x o_2 b o_2 y = (a o_2 b) o_2 (x o_2 y) \in A$. As $x o_2 y \in A$ and $a o_2 b \in \bar{A}$.

Now $(r o_1 x \in A \text{ and } r o_2 x \in A)$.

Therefore $r o_1 a \in \bar{A}$ and $r o_2 a \in \bar{A}$. Similarly, $a o_1 r \in \bar{A}$ and $a o_2 r \in \bar{A}$.

Hence $\bar{A}$ is an ideal of S . Next consider an element c such that $c o_1 d \in \bar{A}$ and $c o_2 d \in \bar{A}$.

Then there exist x and y in A such that $c o_1 x \in A$, $c o_2 y \in A$ and $c o_1 d o_1 y \in A$, $c o_2 d o_2 y \in A$.

$$d o_1 (c o_1 x o_1 y) = (c o_1 d o_1 y) o_1 x \in A \text{ and } c o_1 x o_1 y \in A.$$

Hence $d \in \bar{A}$ and $\bar{A}$ is a k -ideal of S . since $a o_1 \bar{a} \in A$ and $a o_2 \bar{a} \in \bar{A} \forall a \in A$.

It follows that $A \subseteq \bar{A}$

6. Radical of Ideals in b-semiring

Definition 6.1 [2]: Let I be a proper ideal in a b-semiring (S, o_1, o_2) , then the radical I is denoted by $\sqrt{I}$ And is defined to be the intersection of all the prime ideals in (S, o_1, o_2) .

Definition 6.2: A proper ideal I in a b-semiring (S, o_1, o_2) is said to be semi-prime if $I = \sqrt{I}$.

Theorem 6.3: If I is proper ideal in a b-semiring (S, o_1, o_2) then $\sqrt{I}$ is an ideal in (S, o_1, o_2)

$$\text{And } I \subset \sqrt{I} = \bigcap_{I_i \in I} I_i$$

Theorem 6.4: If I is a prime ideal in a b-semiring (S, o_1, o_2) , then I is semi-prime ideal.

Proof: we have from theorem 5.3. $I \subset \sqrt{I} \rightarrow (i)$

Let $\{B_i\}_{i \in I}$ be the collection of all prime ideals in (S, o_1, o_2) that contains I .

Clearly, $I \in \{B_i\}_{i \in I}$ and $\sqrt{I} = \bigcap_{i \in I} B_i \subset I$, thus $I = \sqrt{I}$.

Example 6.5: Let $(P(X), \cup, \cap)$ be a b-semiring and let

$$I = \{\{\varnothing, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{ab\}\}, \cap, \cup\} \text{ be an ideal of } (P(X), \cup, \cap).$$

Further suppose $\{B_i\}_{i \in I}$ be the intersection of all such ideals $\sqrt{I} = \bigcap_{i \in I} B_i \subset I \Rightarrow I = \sqrt{I}$.

Definition 6.5: Let S_1 be a subset of a b-semiring (S, o_1, o_2) , An Ideal P of S is said to be maximal With respect to S_1 provided;

(i) $P \cap S_1 = \emptyset$

(ii) If A is an ideal of S such that $P \subsetneq A$, then $A \cap S = \emptyset$

Theorem 6.6: If I is a proper ideal in a b-semiring (S, o_1, o_2) , then $\sqrt{I} = \{x \in S/n \in \mathbb{N} \text{ such that } x^n \in I\}$.

Here (S, o_1, o_2) is a b-semiring and

$$x^n = x o_1 x o_1 x o_1 x o_1 \dots \dots n - \text{times.}$$

$$x^n = x o_2 x o_2 x o_2 x o_2 \dots \dots n - \text{times. Where } n \in \mathbb{N}.$$

Proof: Let (S, o_1, o_2) is a b-semiring and $x \in S$.

$$x^n = x o_1 x o_1 x o_1 x o_1 \dots \dots n - \text{times} \rightarrow A.$$

$$x^n = x o_2 x o_2 x o_2 x o_2 \dots \dots n - \text{times}$$

Let P be a prime ideal in (S, o_1, o_2) that contains.

Since P is prime and from Equation $A \Rightarrow x \in P$.

Since P is an arbitrary prime ideal in S .

It follows that $x \in \sqrt{I}$. Conversely assume that $x \in \sqrt{I}$. such that

$$x o_1 x o_1 x o_1 x o_1 \dots \dots n - \text{times} \notin I \text{ and} \tag{B}$$

$$x o_2 x o_2 x o_2 x o_2 \dots \dots n - \text{times} \notin I \text{ for } n \in \mathbb{N}.$$

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Choosing any such x from equation B. We have,

$$\text{Let } S_1 = \{x o_1 x o_1 x o_1 x o_1 \dots \dots o_1 x o_1 x \text{ and } x o_2 x o_2 x o_2 x o_2 \dots \dots o_2 x o_2 x / n \in \mathbb{N}\}$$

Since S_1 is closed in S with respect to o_1 and o_2 such that $S_1 \cap I \neq \emptyset$,

then there exist an ideal P in S , such that $I \subset P$ and P is maximal with respect to S .

And $\Rightarrow P$ is Prime in S , Since $P \cap S = \emptyset$ and $x \in S$,

And it follows $x \notin \sqrt{I}$, which is a contradiction.

Corollary 6.7: If I is a proper Ideal in a b-semiring (S, o_1, o_2) then $\sqrt{I}$ is semiprime.

Proof: we know that Radical of I is a proper ideal in (S, o_1, o_2) ,

$$\text{And we have } \sqrt{I} \subset \sqrt{\sqrt{I}}, \text{ Let } x \in \sqrt{\sqrt{I}},$$

Then we have from previous theorem, that $\exists n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that

$$x o_1 x o_1 x o_1 x o_1 \dots \dots n - \text{times} \in \sqrt{I}$$

$$x o_2 x o_2 x o_2 x o_2 \dots \dots n - \text{times} \in \sqrt{I}$$

And now taking $m \in \mathbb{N}$ such that

$$(x o_1 x o_1 x o_1 x o_1 \dots \dots o_1 x o_1 x)^m \in I.$$

$$(x o_2 x o_2 x o_2 x o_2 \dots \dots o_2 x o_2 x)^m \in I.$$

$$\text{Thus } x_{11} o_1 x_{22} o_1 x_{33} o_1 \dots \dots o_1 x_{nm} \in I$$

$$\text{And } x_{11} o_2 x_{22} o_2 x_{33} o_2 \dots \dots o_2 x_{nm} \in I. \text{ and hence } x \in \sqrt{I}.$$

Corollary 6.8: Let I_1 and I_2 be two ideals in a b-semiring (S, o_1, o_2)

If (i) $I_1 \subset I_2$ then $\sqrt{I_1} \subset \sqrt{I_2}$.

(ii) if $I_1 \cap I_2 \neq \emptyset$ then $\sqrt{I_1 \cap I_2} = \sqrt{I_1} \cap \sqrt{I_2}$.

Proof: (i) If $x \in \sqrt{I_1}$ then $\exists n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that

$$x o_1 x o_1 x o_1 x o_1 \dots \dots n - \text{times} \in I_1 \subset I_2$$

$$x o_2 x o_2 x o_2 x o_2 \dots \dots n - \text{times} \in I_1 \subset I_2$$

Hence $x \in I_2 \Rightarrow x \in \sqrt{I_2}$. Therefore $\sqrt{I_1} \subset \sqrt{I_2}$.

(ii) Since I_1 and I_2 are two ideals of (S, o_1, o_2) and $I_1 \cap I_2 \neq \emptyset$,

It is obvious that $I_1 \cap I_2$ is an ideal in S . Let $x \in \sqrt{I_1 \cap I_2}$. Then there exists an $n \in \mathbb{N}$

Such that $x o_1 x o_1 x o_1 x o_1 \dots \dots n - \text{times} \in I_1 \cap I_2$ and

$$x o_2 x o_2 x o_2 x o_2 \dots \dots n - \text{times} \in I_1 \cap I_2.$$

Therefore

$$x o_1 x o_1 x o_1 x o_1 \dots \dots n - \text{times} \in I_1$$

$$x o_2 x o_2 x o_2 x o_2 \dots \dots n - \text{times} \in I_1.$$

And $x o_1 x o_1 x o_1 x o_1 \dots \dots n - \text{times} \in I_2$,

$$x o_1 x o_1 x o_1 x o_1 \dots \dots n - \text{times} \in I_2.$$

And it follows that $x \in \sqrt{I_1}$ and $x \in \sqrt{I_2}$. Hence $x \in \sqrt{I_1} \cap \sqrt{I_2}$.

Thus $\sqrt{I_1 \cap I_2} = \sqrt{I_1} \cap \sqrt{I_2}$.

Definition 6.9: Let I be an ideal in a b-semiring (S, o_1, o_2) . A prime ideal M in S is called a minimal prime (completely prime) divisor of I provided .

(i) $I \subset M$.

(ii) If C is prime (completely prime) ideal in S such that

$$I \subseteq C \subset M, \text{ then } C = M.$$

Theorem 6.10: If I be a proper Ideal in a b-semiring (S, o_1, o_2) , then there exist a minimal Prime divisor Of I moreover if P is a Prime Ideal in S , such that $I \subset P$ then there exist a minimal prime divisor M of I Such that $I \subset M \subset P$.

Proof: Let I be proper Ideal in a b-semiring (S, o_1, o_2) . Then there exist a prime ideal in .

Let that ideal be P , again suppose C be any prime ideal in S ,

$$\text{Be such that } F = \{C \subset P / I \subset C\}$$

Now define a relation $\leq$ on F be such that $C_1 \leq C_2 \Rightarrow C_1 \subset C_2$.

F be a partially ordered set under the relation $\leq$.

Let $\{C_i\}_{i \in I}$ be a non empty chain in F ,

Clearly $\bigcap_{i \in I} C_i$ is an ideal in S .

$$\text{Therefore } I \subset \bigcap_{i \in I} C_i \subset P \text{ and } \bigcap_{i \in I} C_i \in F$$

And it can be shown $\bigcap_{i \in I} C_i$ is prime. Let $a, b \in S$

Such that $a o_1 b \in \bigcap_{i \in I} C_i$ and $a o_2 b \in \bigcap_{i \in I} C_i \Rightarrow a o_1 b \in C_i$ and $a o_2 b \in C_i$ for each $i \in I$.

Suppose $\exists i_0 \in I$ such that $a \notin C_{i_0}$ and C_{i_0} is prime $\Rightarrow b \in C_{i_0}$.

Let $C_i \in \{C_i\}_{i \in I}$ If $C_i \subset C_{i_0}$, then $b \in C_i$ otherwise C_i is prime implies

$a \in C_i \subset C_{i_0}$ A contradiction. If $C_{i_0} \subset C_i \Rightarrow b \in C_i$. Since $\{C_i\}_{i \in I}$ is a chain in F

it follows $b \in C_i$ for any $i \in I$. i.e, $b \in \bigcap_{i \in I} C_i$,

Consequently $\bigcap_{i \in I} C_i$ is prime, therefore $\bigcap_{i \in I} C_i \in F$.

By Zorn's Lemma
 $\implies \bigcap_{i \in I} C_i$ is maximal in F .

Let one of the maximal be M and let D be the prime ideal in S , such that

$$I \subseteq D \subset M. \Rightarrow D \in F \text{ And } M \leq D.$$

Since M is the maximal in F , it follows that $D = M$. Therefore M is minimal prime divisor of I .

Theorem 6.11: If I is a proper Ideal in a b-semiring (S, σ_1, σ_2) . then the radical of I is intersection of all Minimal prime divisor of I .

Proof: Let $\{I_i\}_{i \in I}$ be the collection of all prime ideals in S containing I .

And suppose, $I^* = \{i \in I / I_i \text{ is a minimal prime divisor of } I\}$

We have to show that $\sqrt{I} = \bigcap_{i \in I^*} I_i$. Let $x \in \sqrt{I}$,

By Definition
 $\implies x \in \bigcap_{i \in I^*} I_i, x \in I_i$ For any $i \in I$

$x \in I_i$ For any $i \in I^*$, Therefore $x \in \bigcap_{i \in I^*} I_i$.

Conversely, Assume $\bigcap_{i \in I^*} I_i \not\subseteq \sqrt{I}$. Then there exists $x \in \bigcap_{i \in I^*} I_i$ such that $x \notin \sqrt{I}$.

Hence there exists a prime ideal B_{i_0} in S such that $x \notin B_{i_0}$.

Since $I \subset B_{i_0}$ and B_{i_0} is prime,

Therefore, we know that there exists a minimal prime divisor

$I_j \in \{I_i\}_{i \in I^*}$ Be such that $I \subset I_j \subset B_{i_0}$. However $I_j \in \{I_i\}_{i \in I^*}$

And $x \in \bigcap_{i \in I^*} I_i \implies x \in I_j \subset B_{i_0}$, which is a contradiction.

C. Bi-ideals

Let (S, σ_1, σ_2) be a b-semiring, A non-empty Subset B of S is called a bi-ideal if it satisfies with both the operation

$$B \sigma_1 S \sigma_1 B \subseteq B \text{ and}$$

$$B \sigma_2 S \sigma_2 B \subseteq B$$

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